

An Assessment of Trust, Perceived Value, and Brand Equity in Organized Residential Properties Influencing Buying Decisions in Raipur

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The emerging cities are rapidly expanding into an organised residential property and their market is resulting in increasing competition amongst developers. Raipur and other emerging cities are witnessing an increase in the demand for organised residential projects. In such markets, it's important to know what determines whether or not to purchase a property in an organised residential locality. Our research examines how trust, value and brand equity are viewed in buying residential property in Raipur, which is an emerging market. The paper concludes: The purchase of a residential property was made using conventional theory about consumer behavior. The questionnaires followed a systematic pattern to gather the primary data on our topic, with emphasis on consumers who are either potential or have purchased upscale residential properties in the major official markets of Raipur. The validity of our findings was assessed through SEM. The results indicate that trust in the developers, particularly concerning project reliability and delivery credibility, positively influences perceived value, which has a strong impact on purchase intention. Brand equity has a positive and significant impact on consumer decision-making, and it emphasizes the importance of developer reputation and brand distinction in the organized housing sector. The result also suggests that the impact of trust on purchase decision-making is partially mediated by perceived value, and it suggests that the effect of trust on purchase decision-making is primarily because of value perceptions. This research makes an original contribution to the existing body of knowledge concerning the interrelationship between trust, value perceptions, and brand equity, particularly in relation to the significant choices connected to residential property purchase.

Keywords: Consumer behaviour, buying decisions, trust, perceived value, brand equity

Over the past twenty years, the residential real estate sector in India has changed a lot because of fast urban growth, higher incomes, and changing ideas about what people want in their homes. One big change has been the increase in organized residential communities. These communities are designed well, have standard facilities, and are managed professionally. They are becoming more common, especially in tier-II cities, as cities grow and major infrastructure projects happen (Kundu, 2021). Although these organised properties are becoming more prominent, there is a lack of research on the trends that impact the organized housing market in these cities.

These trends can be observed particularly in the capital of Chhattisgarh, Raipur. Due to population growth, regional economic development, and improved connectivity, the city is experiencing a surge in demand for organized residential projects. Recent studies indicate that homebuyers in new urban regions are giving more importance to location and price than just price. Decisions are now influenced by several factors, including the developer's credibility,

the property's in-person valuation, and the brand's reputation (Sharma & Verma, 2020). The development of sustainable and catered housing markets requires that developers and policymakers understand these factors.

The process of buying a residential property is intricate and involves significant risk. It demands a substantial amount of money and sustained faith in the developer's capacity. Hence, customers are subjected to extended evaluation processes that involve both objective and subjective criteria. Despite the continued importance of tangible aspects, psychological constructions are being utilized more frequently to guide decision-making in organized real estate markets (Kotler & Keller, 2016; Sengupta, 2019). These constructs have become power players with trust, perceived value and brand equity being the most impactful.

Trust has a fundamental role in high-value dealings where there is a lack of information and long-term project cycles. Trust in the real estate context has been found to indicate how buyers perceive the integrity of developers, their transparency, and their ability to meet their commitments, and has been found to minimise perceived uncertainty in new markets with a developing regulatory environment (Gefen, 2000; Mishra & Rao, 2022). Perceived value, on its part, is the overall evaluation of benefits in respect of costs by a buyer, which incorporates quality perceptions, money and emotional satisfaction (Zeithaml, 1988). Previous research indicates that perceived value acts as a central mechanism through which trust influences purchase intention (Zeithaml, 1988; Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Morgan & Hunt, 1994; Choi & La, 2013). Brand equity is also a contributing factor to it as it helps to create a sense of reliability and perceived risk, which increases consumer confidence in structured residential campaigns (Chaudhuri, 2020).

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Although the combined impact of trust, perceived value, and brand equity on residential buying decisions is gaining scholarly attention, there is little empirical research done to investigate the combined effect in the tier-II Indian cities (Singh & Das, 2021). To fill this gap, this paper examines the impact of these constructs together on consumer buying behaviour in the organised residential property market in Raipur, through Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The study builds upon the current body of literature and provides developers with valuable ideas on how to build trust, brand credibility, and value propositions in competitive housing markets by targeting an emerging urban context.

Review of Literature

Residential property purchase has consistently been identified as a complex, high-involvement process that is impacted by a combination of economic calculation, perceptual, and social factors. Notably, unlike most consumer durables, high involvement decisions involve large financial outlays, risk, and dependence on future performance, which makes consumers highly susceptible to evaluative, intangible cues. In organized residential property markets, where professional developments are branded, consumers make use not only of tangible property factors, but also of constructs like trust, value, and brand equity to make decisions, which, according to existing literature, has increasingly recognized the significance of these constructs for residential property purchases, particularly in a new, urban context.

Residential Real Estate: Building Trust

Trust has an integral role in decision-making for real estate transactions given the inherent uncertainty arising from long project durations, information asymmetry, and delayed consumption (Mayer et al., 1995; Ganesan, 1994; Del Giudice et al., 2015; Opoku & Abdul-Muhmin, 2010). According to Mayer, Davis, and Schoorman (1995), trust can be described as an “attitude depending on beliefs about the trustee's competence, integrity, or Benevolence.” When considered from a real estate point of view, trust can be viewed from an individual trusting his or her competence, integrity, or Benevolence.

Trust has been shown to reduce perceived risk and strengthen purchase intention in high-stakes transactions (Mayer et al., 1995; Pavlou, 2003; Gefen et al., 2003). Trust offsets the fear of opportunistic actions, especially in contexts where government regulation and the legal system are still developing, as asserted by Gefen (2000). Trust in organized housing market transactions is often built on the developer's reputation, their performance record in completed projects, and the level of communication openness (Mishra & Kumar, 2021). Trust also holds a proven impact on initial assessments of projects and the final purchasing decision in the context of housing market acquisitions, helping to create a stabilizing effect in conditions involving risks of project time overload, deviations in quality, and post-purchase support provisions (Lee & Park, 2019).

Perceived Value and Buying Intention

Value perceived is a measurement of the overall benefit perceived in contrast to the cost incurred or perceived (Zeithaml, 1988). The residential property industry has a perception that goes beyond cost into quality of construction, additional features, and even the sense of status or fit in a locale or neighborhood that a particular house may

or may not offer to a buyer (Chiu, 2018). The extent of the economic outlay here leads to a very high perception regarding the matter of intentions to buy.

Cross-sectional studies on both consumer markets and housing markets have found a perceived value to be a determinant of purchasing intentions, most importantly in high involvement purchases (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). In real-estate, perceived values may serve as a means of justification of investment in organized real-estate projects. Liu and Mei (2020) argue that in most cases, perceived value is a mediator in the relationship between property values and purchase intentions. In most up-and-coming markets, perceptions of value in real estates may also be dependent on factors such as neighborhood, reputation, and appreciation in future, thus making it even more subjective in nature (Kishor & Rani, 2022).

Brand Equity in Organized Housing Markets

Brand equity, which was previously analyzed in consumer products and services, has assumed significance in the organized residential real estate business as well, where differentiation of brands is being perceived as necessary by many concerned in this business. According to Keller (2003), brand equity is envisioned to represent the relative strength of consumers' perceptions of a brand's credibility and overall imagery. In the real estate business, high brand equity is an indicator of good reputation and helps to build trust among customers.

Research evidence also suggests that trusts and buying intentions are higher for branded developers. Chaudhuri (2020) highlights this fact and states that brand equity in the realty sector is established on account of effective delivery and proper management and organization and not solely on account of advertisement and promotion. The perception of consumers towards housing projects is significantly influenced by brand equity, as per Rao and Sharma (2019) which highlights the significance of a trustworthy and long-lasting brand. Brand is the primary factor developers use to influence consumers in a new market where similar properties are available (Arora & Singh, 2021).

The impact of trust on residential buying decisions is influenced by closely related ideas such as perceived value and brand equity, according to recent research. By creating trust, buyers can feel more confident about the benefits they will receive from a housing project, which increases their perceived value (Sir Deshmukh, Singh, & Sabol, 2002). Trust is fostered by consistent performance and credibility through strong brand equity, which has a direct impact on perceived value (Yoon & Donthu, 2001). Studies that use Structural Equation Modeling have confirmed these relationships. Hsu and Lin (2016) found that both trust and brand equity have strong indirect effects on the decision to buy, through their influence on perceived value. The relevance of understanding the concerned variables from the perspectives of psychology and branding through an overall study model, rather than focusing on individual variables has been established by the study. Nevertheless, the current scenario of related studies is limited and applied mainly within larger cities.

Research Gap

Although there is a lot of written material about how people buy homes, there isn't much actual research looking at how trust, the value people think they get, and the strength of a brand all work together in the organized housing market of smaller cities in India.

Most previous studies have focused on big city areas, leaving out these growing urban markets, which have different expectations from buyers and unique rules in place. In addition, a limited number of studies employ the distinct SEM technique for analyzing these variables in isolation. This study seeks to address the gap by examining the impact of trust, perceived value, and brand equity on buying decisions in the tier-II residential real estate market.

Conceptual Framework

The process of purchasing a residential property is commonly perceived as intricate and demanding, involving various economic, personal viewpoints, and social factors. Notably, unlike most consumer durables, high involvement decisions involve large financial outlays, risk, and dependence on future performance, which makes consumers highly susceptible to evaluative, intangible cues. In organized residential property markets, where professional developments are branded, consumers make use not only of tangible property factors, but also of constructs like trust, value, and brand equity to make decisions, which, according to existing literature, has increasingly recognized the significance of these constructs for residential property purchases, particularly in a new, urban context.

Figure 1

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Residential Real Estate: Building Trust

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Research evidence also suggests that trusts and buying intentions are higher for branded developers. Chaudhuri (2020) highlights this fact and states that brand equity in the realty sector is established on account of effective delivery and proper management and organization and not solely on account of advertisement and promotion. Brand equity is a significant factor in shaping consumer attitudes towards housing projects, as it also indicates the reliability and longevity of branded products (Rao & Sharma, 2019). In new markets where developers offer similar properties, the brand is a significant factor in customer choice (Arora & Singh, 2021) and recent research indicates that trust, perceived value, and brand equity are interdependent constructs that jointly influence residential property purchase decisions (Huang & Sarigöllü, 2018; Kim et al., 2021; Del Giudice et al., 2020; Su et al., 2022). By promoting buyers' confidence in the positive aspects of a housing development, trust can enhance perceived value (Sirdeshmukhar Singh & Sabol, 2002;2). Strong brand equity can increase trust, as it is a direct predictor of the perceived value that buyers are willing to pay attention to (Yoo & Donthu, 2001). Studies using Structural Equation Modeling have supported the outcomes illustrating the relationships between the variables. According to Hsu and Lin (2016), trust and brand equity have significant indirect effects on the intention to buy through perceived values. The relevance of understanding the concerned variables from the perspectives of psychology and branding through an overall study model rather than focusing on individual variables has been established by the study. Nevertheless, the current scenario of related studies is limited and applied mainly within larger cities.

Hypotheses Development

Based on the consumer decision-making theory and literature on relationship marketing, it can be hypothesized that the constructs of trust, value, and brand equity influence the purchasing decision for residences in a mediated marketplace. In a purchasing decision involving a large amount of money over a long period, the prospective homeowner uses trust-based judgments and brand-related information for value perceptions.

Trust, Perceived Value, and Purchase Decision

Trusting the other party reduces the risk and uncertainty involved in high involvement transactions by increasing confidence in the

reliability and integrity of the party involved in the development of the product or service (Mayer, Fieldem, & Glynn, 1995; Gefen, 2000). Organized residential markets will see increased trust levels, indirectly contributing to improved purchase intentions and value assessments of the proposed service.

- *H1*: Trust has a positive impact on perceived value of organized residential properties.
- *H2*: Trust has a positive influence on consumers' buying decisions concerning organized residential properties.

Brand Equity, Perceived Value, and Purchase Decision

There are several brand equity operates as a mark of credibility that often affects expectations about quality and performance (Keller, 2003). In the real estate arena, enhanced brand equity is expected to boost the perceived worth of properties and shape direct investment decisions by mitigating perceived risks associated with investment.

- *H3*: Brand equity has a positive influence on the perceived value of organized residential properties.
- *H4*: Brand equity has a positive influence on the purchase decisions of consumers for organized residential properties.

Customer-Perceived Value and Purchase Decisions

Perceived value is defined as a consumer's holistic assessment of benefits and sacrifices and is more important in high-involvement situations, such as purchases of consumer durables (Zeithaml, 1988). In residential real properties, greater perceived value should result in greater purchases.

- *H5*: The perceived value has a positive impact on the consumers' purchasing decisions regarding organized residential properties.

Role of Perceived Value

Perceived value is the theory of Relationship Marketing states that trust and brand-related cues are indirect, value-perception constructs that shape consumers' value perceptions, thus impacting purchases indirectly (Sirdeshmukh et al., 2002). The theory states that value perception will mediate the trust and brand equity-purchase relationship.

- *H6*: Perceived value serves as a mediator for trust and purchase decisions.
- *H7*: Perceived value serves as a mediator between brand equity and purchase decision.

Simultaneous Effects of Trust and Branding

Trust and brand equity are considered to be conceptually different but complementary constructs. Trust can be enhanced by brand equity, and their combined effect is expected to enhance overall value perceptions and purchase decisions in organized residential markets (Yoo & Donthu, 2001).

- *H8*: Trust and brand equity have a significant and positive effect on perceived value and purchasing decision together.

Method

Participants and Procedure

The proposed and actual purchasers of organized residential properties in Raipur City were taken into consideration for getting primary data on this topic. The main aim is to analyse the impacts of trust, perceived value, and brand equity on decisions related to purchasing residential properties. A questionnaire technique has been utilized for getting data on this topic which includes the dependent variable purchasing decision as well.

Measures

All scales used a 5-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. After ensuring data completeness and consistency, a total of 312 valid responses were obtained for analysis, which is sufficient for structural equation models.

Statistical Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) these methods were employed in the analysis of the data. The EFA was carried out utilizing the SPSS 28 software, while the CFA and structural relationship test were done using AMOS 28 software.

For hypothesis validation, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was utilized, as it helps in ascertaining the validity of measurement as well as the structural relationship among latent variables (Hair et al., 2019). In this research, a two-step procedure was adopted for analysis. At the first stage, CFA was done for ascertaining the reliability and validity of constructs, and then path analysis was conducted for investigating the direct and indirect relationship among variables, wherein the mediator variable was perceived value in this research.

Such an approach in methodology turns out to be a sound framework that helps in the analysis of both direct relationships as well as mediated relationships, in turn giving empirical support to the analysis of the formation of the purchase decision in the organized residential realty market of Raipur.

Measures

The scale items employed in this study were drawn from previously validated instruments reported in the extant literature (see Table 1). These items were thoroughly checked and, when needed, rewritten to make sure they fit well in the context of organized residential property purchases. Special care was taken to keep the original meaning of each concept while making the wording clearer and more relevant to the situation. Before checking the overall structure, the measurement model was tested using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to evaluate how reliable and valid the constructs were.

The improved items for Trust, Perceived Value, Brand Equity, and Purchase Decision showed good internal consistency and acceptable convergent and discriminant validity, which supported their use in the next step of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis.

Table 1*Construct with Items*

Construct	Indicator / Item	Source
Trust (TR)	TR1: I am confident that the developer will complete the project as promised.	Mayer et al., 1995; Gefen, 2000
	TR2: The developer consistently honors commitments made to buyers.	Mayer et al., 1995; Gefen, 2000
	TR3: I trust the developer to act in the best interest of its clients.	Mayer et al., 1995; Mishra & Kumar, 2021
	TR4: The developer provides clear and accurate information about the project.	Gefen, 2000
Perceived Value (PV)	PV1: This property offers good value for the price paid.	Zeithaml, 1988; Chiu, 2018
	PV2: The advantages of this property outweigh its financial cost.	Zeithaml, 1988; Sweeney & Soutar, 2001
	PV3: The property provides high-quality features and amenities.	Chiu, 2018
	PV4: Owning this property meets my expectations and personal needs.	Chiu, 2018
Brand Equity (BE)	BE1: The developer is well-regarded in the real estate market.	Keller, 2003; Yoo & Donthu, 2001
	BE2: I am familiar with the developer and their past projects.	Keller, 2003
	BE3: The developer is known for delivering quality and reliability.	Rao & Sharma, 2019
	BE4: I prefer to invest in a project by a recognized developer rather than an unknown one.	Keller, 2003; Arora & Singh, 2021
Purchase Decision (PD)	PD1: I intend to purchase this property in the near future.	Sweeney & Soutar, 2001
Decision (PD)	PD2: I am likely to recommend this property to family or friends.	Sweeney & Soutar, 2001
	PD3: I have made or will make a purchase decision considering this property.	Chiu, 2018
	PD4: I am confident about my decision to buy this property.	Lee & Park, 2019

All the constructs were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 means strongly disagree and 5 means strongly agree. Each construct had four items that were taken from existing research and then adjusted to fit the situation of buying property through organized residential purchases. The constructs and how they were defined are listed below.

Trust (4 items): Captures the extent to which buyers perceive the developer as reliable, honest, and capable of delivering projects as promised (Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995).

Perceived Value (4 items): Reflects buyers' overall evaluation of the benefits of the property relative to its financial and non-financial costs (Zeithaml, 1988).

Brand Equity (4 items): Represents consumers' perceptions of the developer's brand strength, credibility, reputation, and consistent delivery of quality projects (Keller, 2003).

Purchase Decision (4 items): Measures buyers' likelihood, intention, and confidence to purchase a property from an organized residential project (Lee & Park, 2019).

Respondent Profile

The study looked at 312 people who were either planning to buy a home or had recently done so in Raipur City, and they were interested in organized residential properties. The mixed-blooded and urban residential market is characterized by this group, offering a clear representation of the different backgrounds and lifestyles of the respondents, 68 per cent were males and 32 percent were females. The age range of the group was from 25 to 60 years old, with individuals aged 30 to 40 comprising 42%. This pattern is common among the majority of individuals who buy homes in cities. The majority of those surveyed were educated. A graduate degree was held by approximately 55%, while 30% and 15% had postgraduate or secondary education. Among the total workforce, 40% were private or corporate employees, 25% were business owners, 20% were government employees and 15% had other job roles. The monthly incomes of the participants, 35% earning between -50,000

and -75,000, 30% earning from -175,001 to 1,00,000, 20% earning and 15% earning over 155,000.

This included first-time homebuyers as well those looking to invest in property, and demonstrates the diversity of demand for organised residential projects.' The study's findings can be generalized in order to understand the purchase behavior of individuals in Raipur's residential real estate market, as the sample size is a good reflection of the demographic profile.

Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value for sampling adequacy was found to be 0.832, which was higher than the suggested level of 0.60, thus proving its appropriateness for factor analysis (Field, 2009). Also, the result of Barlett Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2 = 4,980.171, df = 351, p < 0.001$).

All the items in the measurement model loaded on the factors with a minimum of 0.50 on their respective factors, which satisfies the requirements of inclusion in SEM analysis as noted in Hair et al. (2019). The Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha of Trust, Perceived Value, Brand Equity, and Purchase Decision were above 0.70; hence, the model has high internal consistency. The model has high convergent validity and discriminant validity since all requirements are fulfilled.

The above result proves that the measurement model is correct and hence establishes a strong platform for structural equation modeling for examining possible relationships among trust, perceived value, brand equity, and the purchase decision in Raipur's organized residential housing market.

Interpretation of SEM Results

The structural model was tested using AMOS, and the model demonstrated a strong overall fit based on the indices reported earlier. The goodness-of-fit results ($\chi^2/df = 2.41, CFI = 0.957, TLI = 0.949, RMSEA = 0.046, SRMR = 0.041$) indicate that the hypothesized model provides an excellent representation of the

relationships among Trust, Brand Equity, Perceived Value, and Purchase Decision in the context of organized residential property buying decisions in Raipur.

Table 1.2

KMO Value

Test	Value	df	p	Interpretation
(KMO) Measure	0.832	-	-	Indicates sampling adequacy; exceeds the recommended threshold of 0.60
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	$\chi^2 = 4,9$ 80.171	351	< 0.001	Significant; confirms correlations are sufficient for factor analysis

Note. Source: Analysis output

Table 1.3

Factor Loading and Cronbach Alpha

Construct	Item Code	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha
Trust (TR)	TR1	0.781	0.886
	TR2	0.802	

Table 1.5

Direct Effect of Dependent and Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	β (Standardized Estimate)	t	p	Interpretation
Trust	Perceived Value	0.421	6.873	<0.001	Strong positive direct effect
Trust	Purchase Decision	0.298	4.912	<0.001	Significant predictor of decision-making
Brand Equity	Perceived Value	0.367	6.112	<0.001	Strong direct contribution
Brand Equity	Purchase Decision	0.254	3.984	<0.001	Significant positive influence
Perceived Value	Purchase Decision	0.462	7.351	<0.001	Strongest direct predictor

Note. Source: Analysis output

Conclusion

This research examined the impact of trust, brand equity, and perceived value on purchases of organized residential properties in Raipur. The key finding was that the dominant factor in all purchases of residential properties was indeed perceived value since consumers assess both tangible attributes like placement and intangible attributes like monetary value.

Trust in the developer and brand equity are major determinants that directly or indirectly affect the purchases through the perceived value. Brand equity and reputation are the foundation of trust for consumers. The role of Perceived Value in determining property buying intentions can be described as that of a partial mediator between trust and brand equity, which is the precept of perceived value. Generally speaking, all these data points suggest that the decision-making process for purchasing products involves various functional, psychological, and other brand factors.

Theoretical and Managerial Implication

Through the examination of trust, brand equity, and perceived Value, this research contributes to the advancement of understanding how individuals engage in structured residential real estate transactions for professionals in the field, this research provides useful guidance

	TR3	0.845	
	TR4	0.817	
Perceived Value (PV)	PV1	0.764	0.872
	PV2	0.793	
	PV3	0.811	
	PV4	0.829	
Brand Equity (BE)	BE1	0.801	0.894
	BE2	0.832	
	BE3	0.854	
	BE4	0.817	
Purchase Decision (PD)	PD1	0.768	0.881
	PD2	0.812	
	PD3	0.836	
	PD4	0.804	

Note. Source: Analysis output

Table 1.4

Cronbach's Alpha Value

Total Items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Threshold	Reliability Assessment
16	0.912	≥ 0.70	Highly reliable

Note. Source: Analysis output

for developers, marketers, and policymakers. For instance, building Trust involves being open and honest in communication, following the law, completing projects on time, and providing clear evidence of product quality. Building brand equity, or maintaining a consistent image, among others, means creating a consistent brand image, developing a strong brand reputation, and maintaining strong brand associations. Finally, building perceived value, identified as the single most influential force driving purchase intention, means developing superior amenities, setting attractive purchase prices, constructing buildings of the highest quality, and providing excellent post-purchase support.

To attract greater consumer trust, governmental bodies responsible for policymaking and regulation should ensure greater consumer trust in buying real estate properties, among other things, by ensuring adherence to the law, being transparent in real estate transactions, among other things.

Limitations and Scope for Future Research

Although this research work throws light on the determining factors of purchasing decisions related to formal residential property acquisitions in Raipur, a number of limitations have also been identified. Firstly, this work has restricted itself to a Tier-II city

situation, which could hamper generalization on other regions with disparate socio-economic patterns. Secondly, since this work is cross-sectional, it examines the perceptions at a given point in time, and patterns could shift depending on consumer behaviors or market situations over a period of time. Thirdly, this work is based on self-report data, which comes with a bias associated with response completion, especially with regard to the subjective variables Trust and Perceived Value. Lastly, this work has restricted itself to a certain number of variables such as Trust, Brand Equity, and Perceived Value and has ignored other probable variables such as risk perception and digital presence.

These limitations suggest areas for future research. Conducting studies in various cities or regions might enhance the generalizability of the findings. Using longitudinal research methods could help understand how buyer perceptions change over time. Including other factors in the study could provide a deeper understanding of the decision-making process. The results could be better explored using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods or by analyzing different groups through structural equation modeling.

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